

Data sharing with Dryad: Finding the right home for human research data

"As a researcher, I'm a proponent of transparency and rigor because it's how others can duplicate our work, validate our work, or build upon it. So I think that it's a very good thing that we share our data."

— Ann Van de Winckel

Researcher: Ann Van de Winckel, PhD, MSPT, PT
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<https://med.umn.edu/familymedicine/research/programs-centers/rehabilitation-science/labs/brain-body-mind-lab>

Title: Finding functionality: Rasch analysis of the Functionality Appreciation Scale in community-dwelling adults in the US

Dataset: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.66t1g1k4d>

Related publication: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fresc.2023.1222892>

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The screenshot shows the Dryad dataset page. At the top, it displays the title and authors: Feng, Sarah; McDaniel, Sydney; and Van de Winckel, Ann. It lists the research facility as the Division of Physical Therapy, Department of Rehabilitation Medicine, Medical School, University of Minnesota, and the publication date as Nov 03, 2023. The 'Data files' section lists several files, including 'Nov 03, 2023 version files' (63.79 KB), 'Nov 12, 2023 version files' (122.93 KB), 'Consent_and_capacity_to_consent.pdf' (65.76 KB), 'FAS_data_10.30.2023_for_DRYAD.xlsx' (52.49 KB), and 'README.md' (4.68 KB). The 'Abstract' section provides an introduction, methods, results, and discussion. The 'Citation' section shows 125 views, 11 downloads, and 2 citations. The 'Subject keywords' include spinal cord injury, medical and health sciences, appreciation, body awareness, body image, functionality, healthy adults, and validation studies. The 'Funding' section lists the National Institutes of Health's National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences. The 'Related works' section includes a primary article with the DOI 10.3389/fresc.2023.1222892.

Dataset overview and analytical application

This study evaluated the structural validity of the **Functionality Appreciation Scale (FAS)** using **Rasch analysis** in 567 community-dwelling adults.

The findings support the structural validity of the FAS for community-dwelling adult populations while highlighting the need to introduce more challenging items to improve targeting. In addition, measurement precision needs to be improved.

Keywords: spinal cord injury; medical and health sciences; appreciation; body awareness; body image; functionality; healthy adults; validation studies

Evolving practices in data sharing

Dr. Van de Winckel noted that data sharing has changed significantly over the past decade largely due to mandates requiring it. She emphasized that increased transparency has strengthened the rigor of research by allowing others to evaluate, reproduce, and validate findings. Dr. Van de Winckel highlighted that this is important for all research fields and that there is a need to replication and validation of findings.

The availability of data repositories now ensures that methods and results are more thoroughly documented than they were 20 years ago, enhancing accountability and reproducibility.

Choosing a data repository

Initially, Dr. Van de Winckel planned to deposit her data in the University of Minnesota's DRUM repository, but she was unable to do so due to restrictions on uploading patient data. As a result, she searched for an alternative and began using Dryad prior to receiving her NIH grant.

Why Dryad?

Dr. Van de Winckel later learned that Dryad was among the repositories recommended by the National Institutes of Health as a preferred option for the National Center for Complementary and Integrative Health (NCCIH). With her university also covering data publishing fees for researchers, choosing Dryad was an easy decision.

She described being extremely pleased with the curation process, emphasizing the thorough review of her data submission and the clear, detailed guidance on what needed to be revised and how to revise it.

Dr. Van de Winckel noted that curation support was especially valuable for first-timers, since, as she put it, you can do your best but "you don't

know what you don't know." Dr. Van de Winckel also appreciated the quick turnaround time by the curators and emphasized that the team was consistently responsive and easy to communicate with.

The more you know

The very first time Dr. Van de Winckel submitted data, she was not familiar with the required README file. Because of that, there were certain elements she had not planned for in advance. Dr. Van de Winckel worked to ensure the README for her dataset was clear and easy to understand for anyone not directly involved in the data collection or with study participants.

Dr. Van de Winckel also noted that, as a first-time submitter, entering the metadata and uploading the data files required more time than expected, and additional effort was needed to ensure the data package was accurate and complete.

Key tips Dr. Van de Winckel offers for sharing data effectively, especially in human research:

1. Provide enough context for reuse. Include sufficient detail so others can actually understand and use the data—not just view it.
2. Provide detailed documentation and guidance for interpretation. For example, give the scoring range of scales and indicate whether higher scores mean better or worse outcomes.
3. Think beyond your own expertise. Prepare the dataset so that researchers who are not in your specific field can still understand and build on your work.

Overall, make data as transparent, interpretable, and user-friendly as possible to maximize its value for others.